

SEISMEC

Supporting European Industry Success Maximization
through Empowerment Centred development

D6.1

Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Plan

AUSTRALO

SEISMEC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135884

© SEISMEC 2024-2027

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message

© SEISMEC Consortium – 2024-2027. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Document information

Grant number	101135884
Acronym	SEISMEC
Full title	Supporting European Industry Success Maximization through Empowerment Centred development
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-51 – Pilots for an innovative human-centric industry
Funding scheme	RIA – Research and Innovation action
Start date	January 1 st , 2024
Duration	48 months

Revision v1.0

Work package	WP6
Due date of delivery	30-06-2024
Actual date of delivery	28-06-2024
Nature	R
Dissemination level	PU
Deliverable lead	AUSTRALO
Author(s)	Diana López (AUS), Marva Arampatzi (AUS)
Reviewer(s)	Marcel Langone (EUR), Lieke van Eijk (EUR), Mihai Pop (TITC), Andreas Almpanis (iED)
Version	v1.0

Abstract

This document outlines SEISMEC’s overall dissemination, communication and engagement strategies, providing specific action plans to reach a critical mass. It also contains the compilation of all early stage promotional actions, brand elements designed and released to execute the outreach plans, including: the project’s identity system and brand templates, online channels, events and future publications.

Keywords

Impact, Dissemination, Communication, Outreach, Engagement, Community

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.1	29-05-2024	1 st deliverable draft	Marva Arampatzi (AUS), Diana López (AUS)
v0.2	20-06-2024	2 nd deliverable draft: updated target groups descriptions (3.1.1), added new visual (3.3) and outreach KPI tables (4.1, 5.1), updated descriptions and visuals in 4.3.1, 4.3.2.1, 4.3.2.3 and 5.3.3, finalized conclusions.	Diana López (AUS)
v1.0	25-06-2024	Final deliverable draft	Diana López (AUS)

Table of contents

1	Executive summary	9
2	Introduction	10
2.1	Purpose and scope.....	11
3	Engagement strategy	12
3.1	Building a stakeholder map.....	13
3.1.1	Our key target groups.....	13
3.1.2	Liaising with other initiatives.....	16
3.2	Breaking the ice.....	17
3.3	Adapting to change	18
4	Communication plan	21
4.1	Main goals	21
4.2	Phases and timeline	22
4.2.1	Plan & Revisit	23
4.2.2	Early bird communication.....	23
4.2.3	Targeted communication.....	23
4.3	Communication tools and materials.....	24
4.3.1	Visual identity	24
4.3.2	Online channels.....	29
4.3.3	Promotional materials.....	37
5	Dissemination plan	43
5.1	Main goals	43
5.2	Phases and timeline	44
5.2.1	Identify & Study.....	44
5.2.2	Outreach & Influence.....	44
5.2.3	Embrace & Accept.....	44
5.3	Dissemination tools and materials	45
5.3.1	Publications.....	45
5.3.2	Online channels.....	47
5.3.3	Events, conferences and workshops	48
6	Conclusions	50

List of figures

Figure 1. SEISMEC stakeholder map.....	12
Figure 2. Stakeholder interactions – how to	18
Figure 3. SEISMEC's Agile Stakeholder Framework methodology.....	19
Figure 4. SEISMEC's Brand Book.....	24
Figure 5. Example of SEISMEC's target personas	26
Figure 6. SEISMEC – main logo, icon, flat colour and B&W variations.....	27
Figure 7. SEISMEC Shift – main logo, icon, flat colour and B&W variations	28
Figure 8. SEISMEC's sitemap.....	30
Figure 9. SEISMEC's official website.....	31
Figure 10. SEISMEC's LinkedIn company page.....	32
Figure 11. SEISMEC's X/Twitter profile	33
Figure 12. Campaign snapshots – SEISMEC's key facts.....	35
Figure 13. Campaign snapshots – Join the SEISMEC Shift	35
Figure 14. Campaign snapshots – Project news and general announcements....	36
Figure 15. SEISMEC Newswave – online subscription form.....	37
Figure 16. SEISMEC's first press release	38
Figure 17. SEISMEC's first slide deck	39
Figure 18. SEISMEC's trifold brochure design.....	40
Figure 19. SEISMEC's roll-up banner design.....	40
Figure 20. SEISMEC branded peppermints	41
Figure 21. SEISMEC's YouTube channel	42
Figure 22. SEISMEC's blog post collection	47
Figure 23. SEISMEC's Open Access repository at Zenodo	48

List of tables

Table 1. SEISMEC's initial list of related initiatives	17
Table 2. Outreach KPIs – Communication.....	22
Table 3. Outreach KPIs – Dissemination.....	43
Table 4. List of SEISMEC’s peer-reviewed publications so far	46
Table 5. List of past and upcoming events in SEISMEC’s pipeline.....	49

Acronyms and definitions

AI	Artificial Intelligence
B&W	Black & White
CAPS	Creativity + Collaboration/ Autonomy + Automation/ Privacy + Productivity/ Safety + Security
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CoP	Community of Practice
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	Europe/European
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Member State
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PR	Public Relations
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

This deliverable sets the framework, guidelines and means for the project's **Communication** and **Dissemination** activities. It also serves as the foundation to design and build a **Stakeholder Collaboration Framework**, developed to identify the ecosystem of key actors impacted by SEISMEC's innovations.

The strategies and methodologies set out in this document aim to:

- Ensure the development of appropriate means of communication of the project's results outside of our consortium, with the intention of raising awareness on the concepts of Industry 5.0.
- Increase the project's impact among the identified target audiences, both for future commercial exploration and market uptake, but also to further research opportunities and ultimately usher in a so-called SEISMEC Shift towards human-centricity within the Industry 5.0 paradigm.
- Onboard key stakeholders into SEISMEC's vision for piloting experiences and the overarching CAPS framework, thus supporting the creation of an EU-wide community around the project, ensuring its continuity and fostering long-term sustainability of its innovations and expected outcomes.

Consequently, this deliverable is a living document, and as such, the Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plans presented will be subject to constant evaluation and revision throughout the duration of the project, so as to have a constantly updated and accurate depiction of the progress made and challenges ahead.

2 Introduction

Our understanding of the broader concepts of employment, productivity and efficiency in an industrial setting has been radically reshaped by recent technological breakthroughs –Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing and intensive data analytics, to name a few–, which have steadily permeated through every single operational layer at the workplace. The growing importance of digitalisation, combined with the ramifications of the Covid-19 pandemic have, in turn, made it apparent that it is time to rethink the demand for flexibilization, collaboration and the desire for fulfilment in the context of workers’ expectations.

Companies are now also faced with the challenge of creating and nurturing motivation within an ever-changing technological playground, which is not an easy task: one-third of organisations have reported strong internal resistance to new technologies in the workplace, which can mainly be traced back to the lack of influence employees and trade unions have on both their adoption and use and the perceived inequalities (e.g. between age groups, gender, educational background...) it seems to inadvertently highlight.

Ultimately, SEISMEC aims to demonstrate how human-centric solutions can effectively empower workers in the co-design and co-development of new technologies, thus facilitating the journey towards a skills-driven and creativity-infused industrial landscape; one that is built around high-quality, sustainable jobs, and prioritises overall worker security and satisfaction. SEISMEC advocates for a multidimensional transformation that hinges on fair and trustworthy technology, ethical incentives, capacity building and democratisation as key enablers to fundamentally change the way workers see themselves and are seen within their organisations.

This paradigm shift, –fittingly labelled the SEISMEC “shift”– intends to usher in a brand new Industry 5.0 framework that is aligned with European values and strikes the right balance between disruptive technology and human-centricity: a

so-called Reciprocal Human-Technology Intelligence that combines human-in-the-loop with user modelling and preference learning, and leverages explainable AI to boost industrial automation and productivity without compromising workers' creativity, collaboration, autonomy, privacy, safety and overall satisfaction.

2.1 Purpose and scope

D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan is the first of WP6 deliverables. It will be followed by a series of periodic updates, in the form of milestones (MS10 – Promotion and exploitation activities deployed) and final reports (D6.2 and D6.3).

The present document has been structured in the following way:

- Section 3 is concerned with our Engagement strategy, where the ecosystem of organisations surrounding the project and our plans for community building are presented.
- Sections 4 and 5 explain the Communication and Dissemination strategy, where the goals, phases, timeline and tools are described.
- Section 6 outlines the Conclusions of this deliverable, where the final remarks about these strategies are charted.

3 Engagement strategy

SEISMEC’s engagement strategy represents the cornerstone for managing and amplifying the dynamic ecosystem of the project. As such, it serves to identify, create and nurture the synergies required to streamline value between the activities carried out by the project and key public and private actors from our main target groups.

Figure 1. SEISMEC stakeholder map

3.1 Building a stakeholder map

As a joint effort with WP1 and WP5, SEISMEC will leverage each partner's networks to build up a project-specific stakeholder matrix that collates information on key players in our target groups – a combination of multidisciplinary profiles coming from academia, industry and policy.

This initial ecosystem mapping will serve as a basis for the stakeholder segmentation that will be then conducted to:

- Localise and segment contacts by target country and expertise (e.g. for our innovation camp, roadshows and workshops, see [section 3.1.1](#)).
- Reach out to partner initiatives operating in the same space (e.g. other EU-funded projects, see [section 3.1.2](#)).
- Identify those actors more receptive to wider communication actions through the project's own digital channels (e.g. to increase incoming traffic to our website, boost engagement in social media or grow our newsletter subscriber base; see [section 4.3.2](#)).
- Target and follow-up on specific collaboration leads (e.g. new inquiries through our website contact form, one-on-one meetings, networking at events).

The knowledge and contacts acquired through this exercise will help identify and designate key profiles to shape SEISMEC's [Stakeholder Board](#), covering the spectrum from policymakers to industrial federations, professional associations, NGOs and social innovators. The Stakeholder Board will be engaged periodically via dedicated workshops around human-centricity and work to ensure that stakeholders' interests and unmet needs are adequately taken into consideration.

3.1.1 Our key target groups

The first approach to mapping and reaching out to a pan-European network of innovation ecosystems is a thorough examination of our value proposition and how it can serve to capture the key target groups – and the segments within them – relevant to unlock and grow the ambition of SEISMEC. Understanding these

profiles in the value chain is essential for achieving the desired impact (i.e. exploring the feasibility of future business opportunities and market competitiveness).

3.1.1.1 European Industry

Target	Managers and workers within our pilots' industrial ecosystems
---------------	---

SEISMEC will shift relationships between technology pushers (managers) and technology users (workers) to blur barriers between both in a synergistic relationship that will benefit worker well-being and European competitiveness in our pilot ecosystems (retail, digital, textile, electronics, tourism, energy & intensive, aerospace & defence, energy & renewables, agri-food, health, construction, mobility & automotive, cultural & creative, proximity & security, platform labour). SEISMEC acknowledges the diversity that the manager and worker categories entail, tailoring outputs to enhance accessibility and relevance to various geographic, educational, cultural, economic and ethnic backgrounds. The consortium involves key European industrial players and worker representatives (CESI) as initial sounding board for wider impacts and outreach efforts.

3.1.1.2 Policy makers

Target	National and local policy makers, EU policy bodies
---------------	--

While policymaking efforts in Europe aim to protect individuals (e.g. GDPR) these are often seen as a trade-off for efficiency rather than a source of European competitive advantage. Through its stakeholder engagement efforts, as well as its final conference, SEISMEC will shift policy outlooks for the industry in a human-centric direction. These will be framed by legislative efforts such as GDPR, the Digital Services Act, the Digital Markets Act, the AI Act, and the Machine Directive, among others. SEISMEC will also put an effort in having involved not only European but also national and local policymakers as supporters of the SEISMEC shift and mission.

3.1.1.3 Partnerships and networks

Target	AI, Data & Robotics partnership, EU Technology Industry associations, H2020 and Horizon Europe partnerships, EDIHs/EIT/EU Innovation Council, Horizon projects
---------------	--

SEISMEC will lean into the influence of initiatives that are already consolidated in the industry 5.0 space to amplify the footprint of the project's results. We will also leverage the consortium's leadership and participation in ongoing relevant initiatives, partnerships and networks to create synergies and collaboration opportunities across the value chain.

3.1.1.4 Technology providers

Target	Software development companies, Hardware providers
---------------	--

SEISMEC brings together a multidisciplinary team of top research-oriented institutions and market-driven organisations that will design, implement and deploy the solutions in the validation sites. For an external diffusion, the project will engage with the wide European Cloud-Edge Ecosystem, including engineers, researchers, platform, service, application and infrastructure providers, SMEs and start-ups, and standardisation and open-source bodies.

3.1.1.5 Social innovators

Target	Ethical researchers, privacy, security and legal experts, digital education providers, health and wellness professionals, human, social and political rights organisations, cooperatives, volunteer organisations and social action groups
---------------	--

Social innovators have a key role in SEISMEC by engaging vulnerable workers that will allow them to break out of their status of vulnerability to one of critical empowerment. Human and ethical factors are compulsory to facilitate a

transformation compliant with the needs of the workforce. Social science disciplines must be involved in order to understand how people interact with advanced technologies, making their design more natural for the user and relevant to the sector.

3.1.1.6 Civil society

Target	EU citizens, environmental advocates
---------------	--------------------------------------

SEISMEC encourages a common understanding of the positive impact of Industry 5.0, which shifts the focus from technology-driven progress to a thoroughly human-centric and sustainable approach. Highly accessible content is produced to engage with the society as a whole: NGOs and citizens as beneficiaries from the broader impacts of the SEISMEC human-centric approach.

3.1.2 Liaising with other initiatives

Scouting and creating collaboration links with related EU initiatives is vital to harness the knowledge and capacity from our advocate ecosystem to create synergies, extending collaborations across the [Industry 5.0 community of practice](#) and reaching out to other sister projects.

In this sense, SEISMEC will consider several collaboration opportunities (e.g. participation in project meetings, attendance and hosting of joint events/conferences, joint publications on shared research interests and potential clustering efforts) for increased reach and visibility. This ambition also includes cross-learning and fertilisation with other members within the Industry 5.0 CoP. An initial list of relevant links is presented below:

Acronym	Full name
Bridges 5.0	Towards a Human-Centred, Sustainable and Resilient Economy
Up-Skill	Up-Skilling for Industry 5.0 Roll-Out

AI Redgio 5.0	Regions and (E)DIHs alliance for AI-at-the-Edge adoption by European Industry 5.0 Manufacturing SMEs
Sure 5.0	Supporting the SMEs SUstainability and REsilience transition towards industry 5.0 in the mobility, transport & automotive, aerospace and electronics European ecosystems
XR2Industry	Tailoring eXtended Reality to Industry's needs
XR5.0	Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era
AI4Work	Human-centric Digital Twin Approaches to Trustworthy AI and Robotics for Improved Working Conditions
PROSPECTS 5.0	Progress Towards Industry 5.0: A smart study on analysis and identification of practices, drivers, success factors and obstacles of transition towards Industry 5.0
INDUX-R	Transforming European Industrial Ecosystems through eXtended Reality enhanced with human-centric AI and secure, 5G-enabled IoT
ASHVIN	Assistants for Healthy, Safe, and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin
SPATIAL	Achieving trustworthy, transparent and explainable AI for cybersecurity solutions
HumanTech	Human Centered Technologies for a Safer and Greener European Construction Industry

Table 1. SEISMEC's initial list of related initiatives

3.2 Breaking the ice

The main goal behind stakeholder mapping is to identify specific actions to guarantee long-lasting impact and sustainability. This exercise also provides a baseline for tailoring SEISMEC's key messages to our audiences, in order to adapt and fine-tune information and resources to each of these profiles' needs.

Thus, this step supports the first interactions with the community around SEISMEC to share our vision, establish a bi-directional feedback and information

flow and set our initial conversion goals in terms of promotion and potential collaboration opportunities (e.g. matchmaking, publishing, joint events).

Figure 2. Stakeholder interactions – how to

3.3 Adapting to change

As the backbone to sustain all these interactions and maintain interest, SEISMEC implements an Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework, a methodology designed to continuously develop, strengthen and revisit communication streams with key stakeholder groups.

Figure 3. SEISMEC's Agile Stakeholder Framework methodology

This methodology relies on a constant, carefully designed throughput of promotional activities and campaigns, conceived to incite and maintain the interest of our audience throughout the project's lifecycle, as per the values of the [Agile Manifesto](#):

- **Individuals and interactions over processes and tools**: ecosystem building is a team-based approach to deliver value as a joint effort. Tools are an important part of projects, but the team needs to work together effectively through productive interactions with the stakeholders.
- **Results over comprehensive documentation**: it is much more valuable to interact with the stakeholders, obtaining continuous feedback and managing

increments of the ecosystem’s snapshot rather than overspending resources in studying and reporting about their profiles and potential objectives.

- **Collaboration over formality**: this framework is designed to promote and facilitate collaboration in the program. The team aims to engage and collaborate with stakeholders to inspect and adapt the vision, so the project will be as valuable as possible.
- **Responding to change over following a rigid plan**: rather than maintaining a fully defined and static vision of the stakeholders from the project, this methodology focuses on building up an ecosystem of interested parts throughout its lifetime.

4 Communication plan

Although communication and dissemination are two interlinked activities, in this document we choose to address them separately, though always in close dependence on one another. It is obvious that similarities and convergences exist and will be examined throughout the whole lifespan of the project.

SEISMEC takes into account the versatility and agility of a coherent communication plan and is adopting a funnelled approach to ensure that a targeted but wide communication towards all possible target groups and stakeholders will be deployed. This approach primarily focuses on generating awareness by conveying key aspects and benefits of the project to all target audiences and end users.

Easy to interpret, understand and recognize visual material will be designed and communicated, allowing SEISMEC's concepts and benefits to become instantly identifiable to a wider audience while growing and cultivating further interest towards the project and its key outcomes. Additional custom content will be produced and communicated towards specialised target groups to create and maintain an active stakeholder ecosystem. Similarly, relevant information will be extracted from project deliverables; interviews with partners, pilot studies, and will be relayed through SEISMEC's communication channels to further support active user engagement.

4.1 Main goals

This Communication plan is driven by some key objectives that are crucial to its deployment. Although communication objectives may be treated as a single block, some relate to specific target groups only and thus, will be approached with specific tools and activities throughout the lifespan of the project.

SEISMEC's overall objectives for communication are to:

- Increase general awareness and interest about the project to build a solid customer base/ecosystem for future dissemination and exploitation of results.
- Communicate technical, scientific results and benefits to specialised target groups and stakeholders.
- Deliver top-level messages about the project to non-technical target groups and audiences.
- Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of SEISMEC to reach the widest possible community.

To effectively keep track of our progress on these goals, the project will follow a list of impact-related KPIs (Key Performance Indicators), as shown in the table below:

Outreach indicators	Targets
Branding assets and printed/digital materials produced	1,000+
Website visitors (monthly average)	100
Total followers in social media (X/Twitter and LinkedIn)	2,500
Social media impressions (monthly average)	1,500
Videos (teasers and features) produced	15+

Table 2. Outreach KPIs – Communication

4.2 Phases and timeline

Communication activities will be implemented in 3 different phases ([Plan & Revisit](#), [Early bird communication](#) and [Targeted communication](#)), which are closely related to dissemination as well. The common goal is not only to create “buzz” around the project, but also to mobilise a community of end users which can interact and provide feedback on other project activities as well.

4.2.1 Plan & Revisit

The first communication phase will start in M1 of the project and primarily aims at planning all activities, setting up the main communication tools and channels (e.g. website, social media), and identifying potential target groups and stakeholders. This first phase also includes the concept of revisiting the plan: whenever this is required, the communication plan will be revisited and adjusted according to the needs or circumstances that may exist at a specific period of time. During this phase, initial communication activities (e.g. press releases) will also take place.

4.2.2 Early bird communication

The second phase will start in M6. During this phase early bird communication activities will take place aiming to communicate on the existence of the project and its forthcoming activities and actions both to a wider public and to specific communities. Emphasis will be given to our online tools and measures as they tend to have a wider reach than traditional measures. During this phase, participation for networking purposes to webinars or other online events, articles over the internet about the project (i.e. CORDIS, etc.) will take place. This phase will span the whole duration of the project as it mainly focuses on communicating the generic aspects of the project to a wide stakeholder base.

4.2.3 Targeted communication

The third communication phase starts around M18 as it requires the project to be in a relative maturity stage while the first, initial and tangible outcomes are released. During this phase, targeted communication activities will take place, such as: crafting long-form articles, blogs or posts specifically to certain project outcomes and benefits, hosting and/or participating in online and onsite events, and producing communication bundles (e.g. printed materials, videos). This phase will complement phase 2 as it focuses on targeted communication actions catering to specific audiences.

4.3 Communication tools and materials

A series of communication tools have been made available to allow the project to reach the right audiences in an accessible, engaging and cohesive way. This toolkit will be tailored to specific communication needs for all phases of SEISMEC's Communication plan.

4.3.1 Visual identity

SEISMEC's complete visual identity was designed and presented during the first month of the project. The official [brand book](#) (see below) includes the project's visual [guidelines](#), branding [assets](#) (logo variations, icons, banners), [typography](#) and [colour codes](#).

Figure 4. SEISMEC's Brand Book

Apart from defining the key visual tools that shape the project's identity system, this brand book also outlines SEISMEC's branding strategy: its vision and mission, target audience and personas, personality and archetypes.

4.3.1.1 Vision and Mission

SEISMEC's ambition can be distilled into 4 core directives ([Understand-Test-Show-Influence](#)). First, we aim to understand the delicate balance at play between workers, organisations and how they engage with advanced technology in a multi-faceted industrial ecosystem. With this knowledge, we will test custom-fit methods and tools that can nurture and enhance human-technology synergies and skills development in Industry 5.0 workplaces. Through this benchmarking, we will show how human-centric solutions can empower a highly skilled, value-driven and increasingly creative industrial workforce in Europe, and ultimately, influence new evidence-based recommendations that seamlessly connect workers, industry, policymakers and like-minded initiatives in the EU sphere.

4.3.1.2 Target audience and personas

In design thinking and branding, personas are abstract representations of an intended target audience or end user. In order to clearly differentiate between profiles within SEISMEC's stakeholder map, a series of fictional personas have been created to help shape the overall behaviour, experience and expectations of the project's potential user base. An example of this exercise is shown in the selected personas below.

Figure 5. Example of SEISMEC's target personas

4.3.1.3 Brand personality and archetypes

SEISMEC is an interdisciplinary project aiming to shape a future of work that is both productive and enriching, with a focus on creating sustainable work environments that prioritise employee well-being and fulfilment. This statement informs the whole project's personality (SEISMEC's core traits, values, priorities and voice), setting the tone for our audiences on what to expect. This personality can be inherently mapped to a set of so-called archetypes – symbolic images that

model specific human traits and that helps us both understand and connect with a brand. For SEISMEC, the main archetypes that we want to highlight and reinforce are the **caregiver** –associated with compassion, generosity and nurturing– and the **explorer** –linked to adventure, discovery and independence.

Figure 6. SEISMEC – main logo, icon, flat colour and B&W variations

Figure 7. SEISMEC Shift – main logo, icon, flat colour and B&W variations

4.3.2 Online channels

4.3.2.1 Project website

SEISMEC's public website is key to maximize visibility of the project, as it is the main entry point to showcase our main ideas and approach, news, findings and results, and serves to introduce visitors to SEISMEC's rationale and educate them on its core concepts.

A complete [sitemap](#) is presented below. The website structure and navigation menus will be expanded and fine-tuned as the project progresses and there is more content hosted online. A first significant update is expected to go live shortly to include the following pages:

- **CAPS Self-Assessment**: a new website section to set the foundations for the CAPS framework – this page will provide comprehensive definitions for all CAPS factors, together with a glimpse into our approach and a set of targeted questions for workers, organisations and industries to assess where they stand in the journey towards human-centricity.
- **Meet The Team**: a dedicated section to introduce our partners and the specific team members directly involved in the project.
- **Advisory Board**: a page to showcase the members of our Advisory Board, a group of international experts to be consulted periodically on critical methodological and regulatory issues and complex issues (e.g. ethics and security).

Website	https://seismec.eu/
---------	---

Figure 8. SEISMEC's sitemap

Figure 9. SEISMEC's official website

4.3.2.2 Social media

Social media channels are a powerful tool to disseminate information to the general public, nurturing their interest and allowing them to directly engage with the content that we provide. General audiences are in fact an important part of our stakeholder base and essential in realising the full potential of the results that SEISMEC is set to achieve.

All activity on our online channels has been planned according to an overarching social media strategy, developed to deliver certain goals that are meant to gain the necessary awareness to carry out an effective dissemination of the project's results. Initial conversion goals include boosting newsletter subscriptions, driving traffic to our website, increasing our Zenodo metrics (views and downloads) and growing our online community of social media followers.

The project's online presence will be established and built around well-known social media channels, with a focus on LinkedIn and X (formerly known as Twitter). These two platforms were chosen after careful consideration of SEISMEC's target audiences, and both profiles were set up prior to the official start of the

project. Social media campaigns have been built to accommodate both platforms, maintaining consistency in messaging and visuals. This approach not only reinforces the project's identity but also ensures a consistent and professional cross-platform presence.

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/seismec>

Figure 10. SEISMEC's LinkedIn company page

X/Twitter https://twitter.com/SEISMEC_EU

Figure 11. SEISMEC's X/Twitter profile

4.3.2.2.1 High-level directives for social media use

The overall strategy pools all available resources to reach a broader audience and get our message across to our target stakeholders. The key elements of engagement are the following:

- **Post regularly:** effective posting on social media relies on consistency. The project employs optimization and scheduling tools (e.g. Hootsuite) to post regularly and at optimal times in the day –when most traffic on X/Twitter and LinkedIn occurs for our target audience–, thus boosting engagement and organic views.
- **Use references, keywords and hashtags:** linking our tweets to other accounts and trending hashtags (e.g. #HorizonEU, #seismec.eu, #industry5.0, #humancentricity) helps leverage on the traction from existing networks.

- **Actively share content from the community:** sharing news and information not just related to our project but also relevant to the wider community around Industry 5.0 (e.g. news of scientific, academic or legal nature from media outlets across Europe).
- **Differentiate posts across platforms:** there are subtle differences in tone between social media platforms, as well as specific platform restrictions to be mindful of. As an example: we might consider capitalising on LinkedIn’s professional nature and more “serious” tone, and the general perception that information there tends to be more reliable. This means that individuals with genuine interest in the topics that SEISMEC deals with will eventually invest more time reading what we share on this platform. For this reason, the information shared on LinkedIn needs to be fine-tuned, through longer text, more detailed information and highly specific hashtags. Conversely, due to character limit, X/Twitter posts are snippets instead, so there’s a need to condense posts down to their core messages.

4.3.2.2 SEISMEC’s social media strategy

During the early stages of the project, multiple campaigns have been scheduled to communicate and disseminate the project's key details (e.g. vision, mission, targets, challenges, team). These recurring posts have run in parallel with ad-hoc communications on specific project news, events and publications. Some examples of these campaigns are:

- **SEISMEC’s key facts:** an overview of the project’s goals, challenges and core ideas, meet the team.
- **Join the SEISMEC Shift:** outlining our vision for a human-centric revolution through the implementation of our CAPS framework.
- **Project updates:** sharing news about SEISMEC, like meeting recaps (e.g. our kick-off meeting), presentations at events and publication efforts.
- **General announcements:** to promote our website’s launch and new blog posts available, boost newsletter subscriptions or share our first press release.

The driving force behind this approach is for our audience to better understand and familiarize themselves with SEISMEC’s core ideas, paving the way for future results to be easily received and contextualized, while effectively increasing our follower base and overall engagement.

Figure 12. Campaign snapshots – SEISMEC's key facts

Figure 13. Campaign snapshots – Join the SEISMEC Shift

Figure 14. Campaign snapshots – Project news and general announcements

4.3.2.3 Newsletters

As an engagement tool, online newsletters can provide a compelling sneak-peek into the project’s main activities and achievements. Our tool of choice is Brevo, a GDPR-compliant mailing platform, where we will periodically design, prepare and send out mailing campaigns about SEISMEC to our [subscriber base](#).

Stay tuned to the SEISMEC project

[SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER](#)

Figure 15. SEISMEC NewsWave – online subscription form

4.3.3 Promotional materials

4.3.3.1 Press releases

SEISMEC will produce and distribute press releases to mainstream and specialist media as well as other relevant outlets to broadcast and highlight the project's key milestones. The first press release for the project's launch has already been published and is accessible through [Zenodo](#) and [our blog](#) on the project's website. Press releases will also be shared internally with project partners so they can use them as reference to communicate about the project through their own networks, channels and newsrooms.

Figure 16. SEISMEC's first press release

4.3.3.2 Slide decks

Well-designed slide decks or pitch decks can be a powerful engagement tool to break the ice and share the project's vision and scope with our audience in a clear and attractive way. Our first official project presentation, outlining the vision, mission, core innovations and team behind SEISMEC is already available through Zenodo [here](#).

Figure 17. SEISMEC's first slide deck

4.3.3.3 Printed materials

Brochures, rollup banners, posters and any other paper-based resource intended for promotional use. Most of this PR material will be available in a digital format, to be printed out when required (e.g. for display in events, workshops, fairs). SEISMEC will also explore other alternatives such as merchandise (e.g. notebooks, pens, stickers, bookmarks, lanyards), showcasing both the project's branding and the official EU acknowledgement. This strategy has proved to be quite effective in reaching a broader audience, while also encouraging a more sustainable approach when considering long-lasting items.

Figure 18. SEISMEC's trifold brochure design

Figure 19. SEISMEC's roll-up banner design

Figure 20. SEISMEC branded peppermints

4.3.3.4 Multimedia

Multimedia material is a self-explanatory and appealing way of introducing the project to a critical mass through well-known channels (e.g., YouTube, Vimeo). To host official presentations, public recordings, interviews and any other video features, the project has set up a dedicated [YouTube channel](#).

The project's YouTube channel will host all multimedia material produced during the project's lifetime, including but not limited to:

- Explainer videos about SEISMEC's core ideas and dedicated teasers for specific promotional campaigns (e.g. International Women's Day 2024).
- Partner features and interviews, video recaps and compilations (e.g. SEISMEC's kick-off snapshots).
- Any other video format (e.g. short video clips for storytelling in social media, pre-recorded podcast episodes...).

YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/@SEISMEC>

Figure 21. SEISMEC's YouTube channel

5 Dissemination plan

Dissemination aims not only to share results with potential users and research peers, the EU industrial ecosystem and other digital players and policy makers, but also to make these results available to the wider community. To this end, SEISMEC has developed a flexible dissemination plan that intends to raise awareness of project results, promoting understanding and encouraging action among key target audiences. The execution of this plan will facilitate the uptake of outcomes and best practices, as well as research insights produced throughout the project's lifetime, thus reinforcing the impacts described in the DoA.

5.1 Main goals

Dissemination goals have been previously described in the DoA. These goals are interlinked with those already set for communication activities and with the overall project objectives: they are all geared towards creating an impact beyond the boundaries of the project. The table below shows the specific KPIs defined to keep track of our dissemination activities:

Outreach indicators	Targets
Peer-reviewed publications (in journals + conferences)	10+10
Non-scientific publications	50
Downloads via Open Access	1,000+
Events + workshops/webinars (hosted and/or attended)	20+10
Industry briefs + Newsletters issued	8+6

Table 3. Outreach KPIs – Dissemination

5.2 Phases and timeline

SEISMEC's Dissemination plan will be implemented in 3 different phases ([Identify & Study](#), [Outreach & Influence](#), [Embrace & Accept](#)). The key difference with the Communication plan is that these 3 phases do not span the whole project timeline, but instead have a start and end dates. Of course, this does not rule out the possibility to extend or adjust any of them if necessary or required.

5.2.1 Identify & Study

During this initial phase, SEISMEC will seek to analyse the project's framework as well as define priorities and actions for the first year of the project, paying special attention to internal and external barriers that might slow down dissemination activities. For this initial phase, a first set of promotional material (produced in the context of SEISMEC's Communication plan) will be prepared and delivered.

5.2.2 Outreach & Influence

The main goal of this second stage is to increase impact and awareness generated during the first phase and showcase SEISMEC's early achievements. All channels will be adequately tailored to find the proper means to engage and collaborate with identified target groups. This will help increase the potential impact of the project's results. Participation in and/or hosting of workshops, ad-hoc events, our innovation camp and webinars will boost the dissemination value as a whole. For this phase, specific promotional material will be produced.

5.2.3 Embrace & Accept

This final phase will leverage the general awareness raised by the two previous phases, with the aim of attracting and onboarding more potential end users interested in SEISMEC's results. All outcomes of the two earlier phases will be evaluated and, if necessary, priorities, measures and dissemination channels will be refined. Participation in events, workshops, conferences, together with

partner contributions to publications in targeted specific media online, printed media and research journals will be key to maximise impact and boost visibility.

5.3 Dissemination tools and materials

As mentioned, Communication and Dissemination activities are inherently interlinked and therefore some tools are shared between both. Below is the list of specific dissemination tools envisioned for SEISMEC.

5.3.1 Publications

5.3.1.1 Project documentation

Documentation material in the form of public deliverables will be made available through SEISMEC’s open access repository at Zenodo (see [section 5.3.2.1](#)) and [CORDIS](#), the European Commission’s primary source of results from Horizon projects. Public documentation will also be accessible through the project’s official website.

5.3.1.2 Peer-reviewed publications

SEISMEC intends to publish and contribute to peer-reviewed publications in top scientific journals in our main areas of research. One of our primary goals is to ensure that technical and clinical achievements and experimental findings are adequately showcased and made available to a larger research community and industrial domains, in order to further collaboration and research.

Category	Title	Authors	Platform
ABSTRACT	Connecting the SMART work design approach to sociotechnical design principles	P.R.A. Oeij, S. Dhondt, F. Vaas	Work Design for Success: Innovative Research and Leading-Edge Practice

JOURNAL	Reviewing workplace innovation as a plea for a practical approach	P.R.A. Oeij, S. Dhondt	Sociology Compass
---------	---	---------------------------	-----------------------------------

Table 4. List of SEISMEC’s peer-reviewed publications so far

5.3.1.3 Other publications

Throughout the project’s timeline, partners will publish and contribute with blogs posts, articles and features. These kinds of pieces can help disseminate the project’s main ideas and results to a wider audience, thus leveraging its impact. A clear example of this kind of informal publications are our online blog under the website’s [News section](#) and its growing collection of short and long-form articles, as can be seen below.

Figure 22. SEISMEC's blog post collection

5.3.2 Online channels

5.3.2.1 Open Access repository

[Zenodo](#) is a part of the [OpenAIRE initiative](#), Europe's hub for open access infrastructure research. Following the European Commission guidelines for Open Science, SEISMEC will provide open access to peer-reviewed publications and scientific research data generated within the project, as per our Data Management Plan. There is a dedicated Zenodo community and repository

already in place for the project, where we will be uploading publications, public deliverables, data, press releases and more as the project progresses.

Zenodo https://zenodo.org/communities/seismec_heurope

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard Log In Sign up

SEISMEC Horizon Europe Project

<https://seismec.eu/> Project Erasmus University Rotterdam ROR, Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research ROR, Technische Universität Berlin ROR, University College Cork ROR, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas ROR, Australo, Transilvania IT Cluster, IED, CESI, SD Worx, Lithuanian Scientific Society ROR, Michelin (France) ROR, Infineon Technologies (Austria) ROR, Thales (France) ROR, Mostostal Warszawa (Poland) ROR, NTT (Romania), Zagreb Airport, Infracap, Kvalitetas, NS Web, Fratelli Piacenza, RRA Zeleni Kras, Arctur (Slovenia) ROR, Malt, Bondi, FARM.NOW, CS-Pointex, Ateş Wind Power

New upload

Records Members About

1 results found Sort by Newest

February 8, 2024 (v1) Other Open

SEISMEC - First press release
AUSTRALO

SEISMEC -Supporting European Industry Success Maximization through Empowerment Centred development- aims to demonstrate the concept of human-centrality across a wide array of industry sectors, scales and sociotechnical contexts in the EU. Through 17 pilots spanning 14 key industrial ecosystems embedded in the European Single Market, SEISMEC will...

Part of SEISMEC Horizon Europe Project
Uploaded on February 8, 2024

179 134

Figure 23. SEISMEC's Open Access repository at Zenodo

5.3.3 Events, conferences and workshops

Our consortium has already been present at a series of events, conferences and workshops that are relevant to the topics SEISMEC is working on.

Below is the relation of events that SEISMEC's partners have attended since the project began, together with a tentative list of upcoming events that might be of interest for dissemination and networking purposes. This list will be continuously updated with inputs from partners and depending on the maturity of the project at a given stage.

Best practices and bottlenecks from SEISMEC, and their discussion in the project's planned innovation camp and future roadshows, will provide the necessary empirical baseline for a shift in European policymaking for human-

centrism by sharing preliminary results from our pilots to bring together, activate and engage them in the SEISMEC community.

Category	Event	Date	Location
CONFERENCE	Work Design for Success: Innovative Research and Leading-Edge Practice	13/02/2024	Perth (AU)
CONFERENCE	SEISMEC: Better work, better workplaces	27/02/2024	Rotterdam (NL)
CONFERENCE	EU Strategy Days Brussels	20/03/2024	Brussels (BE)
CONFERENCE	Hannover Messe 2024 - Enhancing Skills for a Fair and Inclusive Transition	22/04/2024	Hannover (DE)
TRADE FAIR	Techtextil	23/04/2024	Frankfurt (DE)
CONFERENCE	Surveillance Futures conference	09/05/2024	Kingston (CA)
MEETING	PROSPECTS 5.0 – From Industry 4.0 to 5.0: Theory vs. practice	29/05/2024	Brussels (BE)
WORKSHOP	Michelin Technodays	04/06/2024	
CONFERENCE	Science Communication in the Age of Artificial Intelligence	06/06/2024	Zurich (CH)
CONFERENCE	CESI Summer Days 2024	27/06/2024	Brussels (BE)
CONFERENCE	The Future of Workplace Innovation	01/10/2024	San Sebastián (ES)
CONFERENCE	AI@Work – Reshaping Work Conference	23/10/2024	Amsterdam (NL)

Table 5. List of past and upcoming events in SEISMEC's pipeline

6 Conclusions

This document has outlined SEISMEC’s Stakeholder Collaboration framework and Communication and Dissemination strategies. All these tasks fall into the scope of WP6, with WP1 and WP5 leading the project’s efforts on the definition and refinement of a research framework for human-centricity based on the CAPS factors and the delicate interactions with policymakers necessary to produce specific recommendations and guidelines for their practical application..

With regards to its [Stakeholder Collaboration framework](#), SEISMEC’s consortium is in the process of identifying and studying different profiles across a wide spectrum of entities that encompasses policy makers and regulators, industry players, researchers, technology providers, social innovators and other advocate initiatives. Our aim is to understand the ecosystem of actors which might be interested in the project’s findings and their most pressing needs, in order to craft a distinctly unique value proposition for each of them. This effort will inform the first steps of SEISMEC’s [Exploitation plan](#) and will ultimately lead to the project’s roadmap for future valorisation of key results.

Moreover, the proposed [Communication and Dissemination plan](#) has been designed with an agile communication methodology in mind, which will enable effective external dissemination of results in a manner that generates real interest and transforms into meaningful engagement with our key target audiences.

This document will thus serve as a preliminary roadmap for SEISMEC’s consortium members to carry out their specific outreach and promotional activities.. Due to its early release and the project’s overall 48-month timeline, this should be considered a living document and as such, any and all changes will be adequately reflected in successive iterations of upcoming deliverables.

